

References

- Abouelrous, A., Zankl, M., & Wulf, A. (2023). Digital twin applications in urban logistics: A systematic literature review. *arXiv*. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2302.00484>
- Batty, M. (2018). Digital twins. *Environment and Planning B: Urban Analytics and City Science*, 45(5), 817–820. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2399808318796416>
- Debord, G. (2006). Theory of the dérive. In K. Knabb (Ed.), *Situationist International Anthology* (pp. 62–66). Bureau of Public Secrets. (Original work published 1956)
- Fiveable. (2023). Sociolinguistics guide: Multilingual signage signals welcome to immigrants. <https://library.fiveable.me>
- Fugazza, C., Sommesse, A., & Miklósi, Á. (2023). *Body-size awareness affects detours around fences at ground level*. PubMed Central. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/>
- Infra Global. (2023). Singapore's digital twin: From science fiction to hi-tech reality. <https://infra.global/singapores-digital-twin-from-science-fiction-to-hi-tech-reality>
- Imrie, R. (2000). Disability and the city: International perspectives. *Urban Studies*, 37(2), 397–400. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0042098002195>
- Kitchin, R. (1998). 'Out of place', 'knowing one's place': Space, power and the exclusion of disabled people. *Disability & Society*, 13(3), 343–356. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09687599826678>
- Landry, R., & Bourhis, R. Y. (1997). Linguistic landscape and ethnolinguistic vitality: An empirical study. *Journal of Language and Social Psychology*, 16(1), 23–49. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0261927X970161002>
- Lefebvre, H. (1991). *The production of space* (D. Nicholson-Smith, Trans.). Blackwell. (Original work published 1974)
- Lefebvre, H. (2004). *Rhythmanalysis: Space, time and everyday life* (S. Elden & G. Moore, Trans.). Continuum.
- Mills, D. S. (Ed.). (2017). *The domestic dog: Its evolution, behavior and interactions with people* (2nd ed.). Cambridge University Press.
- Palmeri, T. J., & Gauthier, I. (2004). Visual object understanding. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, 5(4), 291–303. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrn1364>
- Pritchard, R., Lee, H., & Yoon, K. (2023). Route choice driven by efficiency, signage, perceived safety. ScienceDirect. <https://www.sciencedirect.com>

Ranftl, R., Bochkovskiy, A., & Koltun, V. (2021). Vision Transformers for Dense Prediction (ArXiv preprint).

Rantakokko, M., Mänty, M., & Rantanen, T. (2020). Walking declines where curbs and crosswalks are poor. ScienceDirect. <https://www.sciencedirect.com>

Ranftl, R., Lasinger, K., Hafner, D., Schindler, K., & Koltun, V. (2020). Towards Robust Monocular Depth Estimation: Mixing Datasets for Zero-shot Cross-dataset Transfer (IEEE TPAMI).

Sheng, K., Liu, L., Wang, F., Li, S., & Zhou, X. (2025). An eye-tracking study on exploring children's visual attention to streetscape elements. *Buildings*, 15(4), 605.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings15040605>

Stemberger, S., Raab, M., & Hoffmann, J. (2018). Children scan crossings from ~1 m eye-level, spend longer searching for moving hazards. ScienceDirect. <https://www.sciencedirect.com>

Testbed Helsinki. (2024). Mobility Lab Helsinki: Developing Helsinki's digital twin for mobility. <https://testbed.hel.fi/en/smart-mobility/mobility-lab-helsinki-develops-helsinkis-digital-twin-for-mobility>

Tong, S., & Bode, N. (2022). Commuters pick the straightest/fastest path. PubMed Central. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/>

Tong, Y., & Bode, N. W. F. (2022). The principles of pedestrian route choice. *Journal of the Royal Society Interface*, 19(190), 20220061. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsif.2022.0061>

Wennberg, H., Phillips, J., & Ståhl, A. (2018). How older people as pedestrians perceive the outdoor environment: Methodological issues derived from studies in two European countries. *Ageing & Society*, 38(12), 2435–2467. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0144686X17000491>